

1-(4'-Bromophenyl)-4,4,6-trimethyl-(1*H*,4*H*)-2-pyrimidinethiol as a Spectrophotometric Reagent for Rhodium(III)

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Pyrimidinethiols also known as cyclic thioureas, constitute a versatile class of analytical reagents¹. Although the reagents² reported for the determination of Rh^{III} are sensitive but require 20–75 min heating time for full colour development. In continuation of our work on the use of such compounds as extractants for platinum metals, gold and copper^{3,4}, the present communication describes the spectrophotometric determination of Rh^{III} with 1-(4'-bromophenyl)-4,4,6-trimethyl-(1*H*,4*H*)-2-pyrimidinethiol (4'-bromo-PTPT). At room temperature Rh^{III} shows no colour reaction with reagent but forms a yellow complex with pyrimidinethiol when heated on a boiling water bath. The complex is extractable in isobutyl methyl ketone (IBMK).

Results and Discussion

Rh^{III}-pyrimidinethiol complex extracted into IBMK from the hot aqueous solution in 2–2.5 *M* HCl containing 10–14% 1,4-dioxan exhibits a sharp absorption peak at 355 nm. The extraction of the yellow complex is quantitative and reproducible. The complex was stable for more than 24 h. It was found that 2.5 ml of 0.02 *M* solution of the reagent is sufficient to extract 20–400 μg of Rh^{III} in a single extraction, higher reagent concentration has no adverse effect but is avoided because of the higher absorbance of the blank. Beer's law is valid over the concentration range 2–32 ppm of Rh^{III}. The Sandell's sensitivity of the reactions 0.039 $\mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$ and molar absorptivity 2637 $\text{dm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1} \text{cm}^{-1}$ at 355 nm. The Job's method of continuous variations and mole-ratio method indicate the formation of a 1 : 2 (metal : ligand) complex.

The effect of large number of diverse ions on the determination of 240 μg of Rh^{III} with 4'-bromo-PTPT was investigated. Initially the foreign ion was added to the Rh^{III} solution in large excess : 100-fold for cations and 500-fold for anions when the interference was intensive, the tests being repeated with successively smaller amount of foreign ion. The tolerance for the foreign ion was taken as the largest amount that would be present to give an error less than 2% in the absorbance at 355 nm. There was no interference from 10 mg each of Cr^{III}, Zn^{II}, Cd^{II}, Mo^{VI}, Cu^{II}, Fe^{II}, Fe^{III}, Ni^{II}, Co^{II}; 5 mg each Zr^{IV}, V^V, Ba^{II}, Sn^{II}, W^{VI},

Mn^{VII}, Mg^{II}, Ti^{IV}, Ca^{II}, Te^{IV}. There was coextraction of Pd^{IV}, Pt^{IV}, Os^{VIII} and Au^{III} but possible interference from these cation is avoided by preliminary complex formation with the same reagent followed by extraction or prior extraction. Ru^{III} interferes in the determination of Rh^{III}. Many anions except thiourea, thiosulphate do not interfere in fairly large concentration.

The precision and accuracy of the method were tested by analysing solutions containing known amounts of Rh^{III} following the recommended procedure. The average of six determinations of 240 μg Rh^{III} was found to have standard deviation 0.005 and coefficient of variation 0.82%. The results of determination of Rh^{III} in synthetic mixture are presented in Table 1.

TABLE 1—DETERMINATION OF Rh^{III} IN SYNTHETIC MIXTURES*

Sample no.	Metal ion added** (μg)	Rh ^{III} recovery %	Relative error, %
1.	Pt ^{IV} , 300; Rh ^{III} , 240	99.8	0.2
2.	Pd ^{II} , 200; Rh ^{III} , 240	99.6	0.4
3.	Os ^{VIII} , 200; Au ^{III} , 200; Rh ^{III} , 240	99.7	0.3
4.	Pt ^{IV} , 200; Pd ^{II} , 300; Rh ^{III} , 240	99.7	0.3
5.	Pt ^{IV} , 300; Pd ^{II} , 200; Os ^{VIII} , 200; Rh ^{III} , 240	99.6	0.4

*Analyses in triplicate. **Prior extraction³.

Experimental

An Elico CL-27 spectrophotometer was used.

Standard Rh^{III} solution was prepared by dissolving RhCl₃·3H₂O (Johnson and Matthey) (1 g) in dilute 1 *M* HCl (AnalaR) and diluting to 1000 ml with distilled water and standardised⁵. 4'-Bromo-PTPT was prepared using 4-bromoaniline⁶, and a reagent solution of 0.02 *M* in 1,4-dioxan was used. All other reagents used of analytical grade.

Procedure : The acidity of Rh^{III} solution was adjusted to 2–2.5 *M* HCl in a total volume of 25 ml and 0.02 *M* pyrimidinethiol in 1,4-dioxan (2.5 ml) was added. The mixture was digested on a boiling water-bath for 10 min and cooled. The yellow complex of Rh^{III} was extracted with IBMK and its absorbance measured at 355 nm against reagent blank.

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